

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF TURBULENT GAS FLOW WITH COMBUSTION REACTIONS

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Abstract: In this work, numerical methods are given for solving the problems of distribution and combustion of methane and an oxidizer a finite velocity in a turbulent flow. In the mathematical modeling of the jet flow, the full equations of the turbulent boundary composition of a multicomponent reacting gas are used. The process of one-stage irreversible combustion is described by the Arrhenius model with constants extracted in the work of C.A. Frolov and recorded. The flow turbulence is described by Sekundov $\nu_t - 92$ equations. Methane is considered as a fuel, air was supplied with a co-current flow. The number of component conservation equations has been reduced with the use of ordinary and reduced Schwab-Zel'dovich functions. Numerical calculations were carried out in dimensionless Mises variables. The used implicit finite-difference scheme provided the second order of approximation accuracy in longitudinal and transverse coordinates. Due to the nonlinearity of the differential equations of substance conservation, internal (in terms of speed) and external (in terms of other indicators) iterative processes were organized. Some results of the computational experiment are presented. The calculation results for the temperature change on the flow axis are compared with the experimental data.

Keywords: mathematical model, turbulent jet, chemical reaction rate, total enthalpy, Arrhenius law, finite differences, numerical algorithm, computational experiment, combustion processes, turbulent model, Zeldovich function, chemical reaction, $k-\varepsilon$ model, mass, velocity, temperature.

Аннотация: В работе приведены численные методы решения задач распространения и горения метана и окислителя с конечной скоростью в турбулентном потоке. При математическом моделировании струйного течения используются полные уравнения турбулентного граничного состава многокомпонентного реагирующего газа. Процесс одностадийного необратимого горения описывается моделью Аррениуса с константами, извлеченными в работе С.А. Фролова и записанными. Турбулентность потока описывается уравнениями Секундова $\nu_t - 92$. В качестве топлива рассматривается метан, воздух подавался прямооток. Количество уравнений сохранения компонент уменьшено за счет использования обычных и приведенных функций Шваба-Зельдовича. Численные расчеты проводились в безразмерных переменных Мизеса. Используемая неявная разностная схема обеспечивала второй порядок точности аппроксимации по продольным и поперечным координатам. В силу нелинейности дифференциальных уравнений сохранения вещества были организованы внутренние (по быстрдействию) и внешние (по другим показателям) итерационные процессы. Приведены некоторые результаты вычислительного эксперимента. Результаты расчета изменения температуры на оси потока сравниваются с экспериментальными данными.

Ключевые слова: математическая модель, турбулентная струя, скорость химической реакции, полная энтальпия, закон Аррениуса, конечные разности, численный алгоритм, вычислительный эксперимент, процессы горения, турбулентная модель, функция Зельдовича, химическая реакция, $k-\varepsilon$ модель, масса, скорость, температура.

Introduction

Combustion is a physical and chemical process, which is a chemical oxidation reaction, accompanied by the release of heat and a bright glow. In the world, jet streams of reacting media are widely used in everyday life, in the production of thermal and electrical energy, in internal combustion chambers, in chemical lasers, in the

production of mercury and building materials, in rocket engine power plants, and in many other branches of technology and production. Depending on the purpose of the organization and the design of gas combustion devices, various problems of facility management arise. In particular, the gas component in the global energy balance is about 70%. Despite the constant

improvement in the performance of gas combustion devices, their efficiency is still very low.

The main problems in the mathematical modeling of combustion processes relate to the description of the turbulence of the flow and the kinetics of the combustion process. Let us dwell on the description of the turbulence of the flow of reacting media.

The choice of the dissipation rate of turbulent energy as the second independent variable for describing the properties of turbulence is very convenient, since, on the one hand, it is possible to obtain a constitutive equation for it under fairly clear physical assumptions, and, on the other hand, this quantity is included in the constitutive equation for the energy of turbulent pulsations. The family of these models is called $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence models, with the help of which individual problems of isothermal jets and jets of reacting gas mixtures are currently solved [1, 2].

The most general analysis of the combustion of unmixed gases was carried out by Ya.B. Zeldovich [3]. One of the first serious attempts to construct a theory of a turbulent plume belongs to Schwab [4], who was the first to develop a general scheme of the process from the standpoint of the theory of free jets. Subsequently, diffusion combustion was studied by the authors of [5] and others.

The flame theory based on the assumption of the generality of the transport mechanism in turbulent jets and in a burning flame is described in [6]. The results of computational-theoretical and experimental studies of the aerodynamics of an axisymmetric turbulent plume are presented, which make it possible to determine the location of the flame front, the distribution of temperature, concentrations and velocity in the cross sections of the flame. A quantitative assessment and a physical explanation are given for such facts known from experiment as an increase in the degree of turbulence in the flame front, and the difference from unity in the values of the Pr and Sc numbers in shear flows. The paper [7] describes a technique and presents some results of a numerical solution of the problem of a turbulent diffusion plume, taking into account the finite reaction rate. Numerical integration of the system of equations of the boundary layer was carried out in the Mises-Mager-Libby plane and using an explicit four-point finite difference scheme. The momentum

equation is linearized. Despite these assumptions, the calculation results agree satisfactorily with the experimental data.

In [8], a mathematical model was developed that makes it possible to calculate the characteristics of a turbulent diffusion flame propagating in an isobaric subsonic flow. It is assumed that a single-stage irreversible reaction occurs between the oxidizer and the fuel entering the flame front. In contrast to the known models of diffusion combustion, the assumption of an infinitely high rate of chemical reactions is not used. In this regard, along with the equation for the average flow velocity and the concentration of the passive impurity, the equation for the average fuel concentration is considered. The rate of a chemical reaction ω assumed to be proportional to the product of the fuel concentration C_f , oxidant concentration C_0 and average flow velocity across the flame $\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \cdot (\omega \propto C_f \cdot C_0 \cdot \frac{\partial u}{\partial z})$, which makes it

possible to substantially simplify the integration of the equations. The system of equations is solved as follows: self-similar solutions of equations are determined that describe the field of average velocity and passive impurity concentration, each of which is closed. When solving these equations, the coefficient of turbulent viscosity is assumed to be constant. Within the framework of the developed model, the position of the flame front is determined, as well as the distribution of temperature, the concentration of reactants in the diffusion flame.

The paper [9] provides an overview of the latest achievements in the field of research on chemical reactions in turbulent flow. Two limiting cases are considered - combustion of a homogeneous mixture and diffusion combustion. It is shown that the assumption of an infinitely high rate of a chemical reaction makes it possible to substantially simplify the description of the combustion process. Calculation methods are analyzed that make it possible to take into account small deviations of the medium from the thermodynamically equilibrium state. It is emphasized that such calculations are especially important when predicting the concentration of toxic agents (nitrogen oxide, soot) in a flame. The influence of heat release on the flow field, in particular, on the characteristics of turbulence, is also considered. Particular attention is paid to the effects associated with density fluctuations. Based

on the analysis performed, it was concluded that the models developed to describe flows with a constant density may be unacceptable for calculating turbulent combustion.

When considering the efficient combustion of gaseous fuel, one should take into account the results of studies of a swirling jet, which are successfully used in the national economy as one of the rational ways to intensify the processes of mixing and combustion.

In [10], the spatial integration method was used to solve the equations describing the axisymmetric incompressible turbulent swirling jet flow. The $k-\varepsilon$ model with isotropic turbulent viscosity is applied. In addition to the distribution of average velocities, such turbulence characteristics as Reynolds stress, turbulent kinetic energy, and dissipation rate are determined. Good agreement with experimental data is obtained. It is shown that the assumption of isotropic turbulent viscosity is quite justified.

The article [11] provides an overview of the work of the Institute of Technical Mechanics of the National Academician of Ukraine and the State Space Agency of Ukraine on gas-phase and heterogeneous reactions and phase transitions and aspects of their application.

In [12], an algorithm and a computer program were developed for calculating compressible turbulent reacting flows by the combined method of large eddies with the closure of subgrid turbulent flows using the filtered joint velocity probability density function and scalar variables (Large Eddy Simulation / Velocity-Scalar-Mass-Filtered Density Function, LES/VSMFDF). The complex has been tested for the problems of an isothermal non-stationary mixing layer, a mixing layer with chemical reactions, and an air flow around a square cylinder. The results obtained are in good agreement with data from the DNS, LES/Smagorinski Subgrid model, and LES/SSM.

An analysis of the scientific literature [1-12] shows that the processes of homogeneous combustion of gases, the main component of which is methane, have not yet been studied enough. Due to the imperfection of the fundamental foundations of chemical exothermic reactions under conditions of a turbulent jet flow, scientific work in this area continues.

Formulation of the problem

A turbulent jet of combustible gas is considered, which flows out of a round nozzle with a diameter of $2a$ and propagates in a co-current flow (in a flooded space) of an oxidizer at a finite chemical velocity.

The velocity distribution in the outlet section of the nozzle and in the co-flow, as well as the initial (at $x=0$) distributions of temperature and concentration of fuel and oxidizer, will be considered given, uniform, homogeneous, and there is also a tangential discontinuity of indicators at the nozzle boundary.

Mathematical model and solution method

In the approximation of the theory of a turbulent boundary layer, the system of equations for the turbulent motion of a multicomponent gas in the presence of a chemical reaction, i.e. combustion, between the components and when the Lewis number for the components is equal to ($Le_i = 1$, i.e. $Pr = Sc_i$), can be written in cylindrical coordinates, taking into account the Sekundov $v_t - 92$ model [13-16]:

$$\begin{cases} \rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \rho g \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\rho (v + v_t) r \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right), \\ \frac{\partial (\rho u r)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial (\rho g r)}{\partial r} = 0, \\ \rho u \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + \rho g \frac{\partial H}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{Pr r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\rho (v + v_t) r \frac{\partial H}{\partial r} \right), \\ \rho u \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial x} + \rho g \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{Sc r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\rho \left(\frac{1}{Re} + v_t \right) r \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial r} \right] + \omega_n \quad (n = 1..N), \\ \rho u \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial x} + \rho g \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r} = P_v - D_v + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\rho r (v + c_0 v_t) \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r} \right) + \\ + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\rho r (-v + (c_1 - c_0) v_t) \right) \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

This system is closed by the following dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned} H &= c_p T + c_2 h_2^*, \quad c_p = \sum_{n=1}^N c_{pn} c_n, \quad p = \rho \frac{R_0}{m} T = const, \quad m = \left(\sum_{n=1}^N m_n / c_n \right)^{-1}, \\ P_v &= \rho c_1 F_2 \left(v_t G_1 + A_1 v_t^3 G_2^2 \right) + \rho c_2 F_2 A_2 N_1 (v + v_t)^{1/2} G_1^2 + \\ &+ \rho c_3 v_t \left(\frac{\partial^2 v_t}{\partial r^2} + N_2 \right), \\ D_v &= \frac{\rho c_3 v_t^2 G_1^2}{a_{sz}^2} + c_4 \rho v_t \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right| \right) + \frac{(\rho c_6 v_t (N_1 d_w + v_{t,w}) + c_7 \rho F_1 v v_t)}{d^2}, \\ F_1 &= \frac{N_1 d_w + 0.4 c_8 v}{v_t + c_8 v + v_{t,w}}, \quad F_2 = \frac{\chi^2 + 1.3 \chi + 0.2}{\chi^2 - 1.3 \chi + 1}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\chi = \frac{v_t}{7\nu}, \quad G_1 = \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right|, \quad G_2 = \left| \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial r^2} \right|,$$

$$N_1 = \left| \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r} \right|, \quad N_2 = \left| \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial r} \right|.$$

$$v_{t,0} = 0, k_s = 0, A_1 = -0.5, A_2 = 4, c_0 = 0.8, c_1 = 1.6, c_2 = 0.1, c_3 = 4.0.$$

$$c_4 = 0.35, c_5 = 3.5, c_6 = 2.9, c_7 = 31.5, c_8 = 0.1, c_s = 0.1, a_{sz} = 0.2.$$

Here and further u, v – average longitudinal and radial components of the velocity vector (ms^{-1}); x, r – longitudinal and radial coordinates (m); ρ, T – density (kg/m^3) and absolute temperature (K) of the gas mixture; p – static pressure (Pa); Pr, Sc_n – turbulent analogues of the Prandtl and Schmidt numbers; C_n – mass concentration n -th gas component in the mixture (kg/kg); ω_n – mass extinction formation rate n -th gas component kg/m^3s ; $c_p = \sum_{n=1}^N c_{pn} c_n$ and C_{pn} – heat capacity of the gas mixture and n -th component at constant pressure $J/kg \cdot K$; h_n^* – calorific value n -th component J/kg ; ν_t – kinematic turbulence coefficient (m^2/s); H – total enthalpy of gas (j).

The gas mixture is assumed to be perfect, therefore its state satisfies the Mendeleev-Clapeyron equation [17-19]:

$$p = \rho R_0 T / m, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } m = \left(\sum_{n=1}^N c_n / m_n \right)^{-1} \text{ and } m_n \text{ – molar}$$

masses of the gas mixture and n -th gas component (kg/mol); R_0 – universal gas constant ($8341.41 J/mol \cdot K$).

The boundary conditions of the problem for the input section $x=0$ are given as:

$$F(O, r) = \begin{cases} F_2 \text{ at the cut of the pipe} \\ F_1 \text{ on satellite treacle} \end{cases}$$

Here $F = u, T, c_n, \nu_t$. The value of the total enthalpy for the inlet section is determined according to the above formula.

At $x > 0$, no flow conditions are specified on the jet axis:

$$\frac{\partial F(x, 0)}{\partial y} = 0, \quad v(x, 0) = 0,$$

and at the jet boundary, according to the F_1 values of the co-current.

Methane is considered as a combustible gas. The one-stage methane combustion kinetics in air is given by the stoichiometric equation

Indexes 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 highlight the parameters of the components - oxygen, methane, carbon dioxide, water vapor and nitrogen, respectively. According to this entry, the molar masses of the components are $m_1 = 32g/mol, m_2 = 16g/mol, m_3 = 44g/mol, m_4 = 18g/mol, m_5 = 28g/mol,$

$\nu_1 = 5 mol, \nu_2 = 1 mol, \nu_3 = 3 mol, \nu_4 = 4 mol, \nu_5 = 0 mol.$ Net calorific value of methane – $50.2 MJ/kg.$

Then, according to [18-19], the reaction rate of methane with oxygen has the form:

$$\omega_2 = - \frac{A}{10^{20} \cdot 4.1868^2} c_1^2 c_2 \rho^3 \exp\left(-\frac{A_{r2}}{T}\right) \left[\frac{\kappa z}{M^3 c} \right].$$

At the same time, for the remaining components, the rate of chemical transformations in the dimensional form is represented as

$$\omega_1 = \frac{\nu_1 m_1}{\nu_2 m_2} \omega_2, \quad \omega_3 = -\frac{\nu_3 m_3}{\nu_2 m_2} \omega_1, \quad \omega_4 = -\frac{\nu_4 m_4}{\nu_2 m_2} \omega_1, \quad \omega_5 = 0 \quad (\nu_5 = 0).$$

Conservation equation n -th component ($n=1..5$) is written as

$$L(c_n) = \omega_n, \text{ where } L(c_n) = \rho u \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial x} + \rho \vartheta \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{Sc_n r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\rho \nu_t r \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial r} \right).$$

The boundary conditions of the problem for the mass concentration of components for the inlet section $x=0$ are given in the following form:

$$\text{At } 0 \leq r \leq a: c_n(0, r) = (c_n)_2;$$

$$\text{At } 0 \leq r \leq r_\infty: c_n(0, r) = (c_n)_1;$$

In particular, if methane is 50% by mass in the composition of the combustible mixture, and oxygen is 50%, then you can take $(c_2)_2 = 0,500, (c_1)_2 = 0,500.$ The composition of the air is taken as $(c_1)_1 = 0,232, (c_5)_1 = 0,768$ [19].

In this case, the remaining concentrations of components at the input of the computational domain have zero values:

$$(c_2)_1 = (c_3)_1 = (c_4)_1 = (c_3)_2 = (c_4)_2 = (c_5)_2 = 0.$$

At $x > 0$ symmetry conditions are set on the jet axis: $\frac{\partial c_n(x, 0)}{\partial r} = 0,$ and at the jet boundary - according to the air flow indicators: and at the boundary of the jet - according to the indicators of the air flow: $c_n(x, r_\infty) = (c_n)_1.$

By virtue of ignoring thermal and barodiffusion, as well as the same values of the

turbulent analogue of the Schmidt number for the components, the convective and diffusion transfers of the components have the same intensity. In this regard, and taking into account the combustion kinetics, we write the conservation equations for five components in the form

$$L(c_2) = \omega_2, L(c_1) = \frac{v_1 m_1}{v_2 m_2} \omega_2, L(c_3) = -\frac{v_3 m_3}{v_2 m_2} \omega_2, L(c_4) = -\frac{v_4 m_4}{v_2 m_2} \omega_2, L(c_5) = 0.$$

Using the first of these equations, we reduce the following three equations to a homogeneous form:

$$L\left(c_1 - \frac{v_1 m_1}{v_2 m_2} c_2\right) = 0, L\left(c_3 + \frac{v_3 m_3}{v_2 m_2} c_2\right) = 0, L\left(c_4 + \frac{v_4 m_4}{v_2 m_2} c_2\right) = 0.$$

At $n = 1, 3, 4$ we introduce the notation

$$\bar{c}_n = c_n \mp \frac{v_n m_n}{v_2 m_2} c_2 \quad (\text{the top sign refers to } n = 1,$$

and the bottom – $n = 3, 4$), write equations in a single form $L(\bar{c}_n) = 0$ and formulate the boundary conditions for the air flow at the inlet in the form

$$(\bar{c}_n)_1 = (c_n)_1 \mp \frac{v_n m_n}{v_2 m_2} (c_2)_1, \quad \text{for fuel flow –}$$

$$(\bar{c}_n)_2 = (c_n)_2 \mp \frac{v_n m_n}{v_2 m_2} (c_2)_2, \quad \text{as well as on the}$$

boundary and axis of the jet.

If we introduce relatively redundant functions in the form of dependence

$$\bar{\bar{c}}_n = \frac{\bar{c}_n - (\bar{c}_n)_1}{(\bar{c}_n)_2 - (\bar{c}_n)_1}, \quad \text{then for the transformed three}$$

equations and the concentration equation $\bar{c}_5 = c_5$ inert gas, the boundary conditions become the same: at the fuel inlet – $(\bar{\bar{c}}_n)_2 = 1$, at the air inlet and at the boundary layer boundary – $(\bar{\bar{c}}_n)_1 = 0$, and

on the jet axis – $\frac{\partial \bar{\bar{c}}_n(x, 0)}{\partial r} = 0$. Accordingly, these equations become mutually equivalent and can be replaced by a single equation for $\bar{\bar{c}}$. In this regard, instead of five equations of the diffusion problem, we solve the equation for $\bar{\bar{c}}$ without source term

For example, the equation for the conservation and transfer of fuel takes the form:

$$\rho_2 \bar{\rho} u_2 \bar{u} \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \bar{x}} + \rho_2 \bar{\rho} u_2 \bar{v} \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \bar{r}} = \frac{1}{Sc a \bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left[\rho_2 \bar{\rho} a u_2 \left(\frac{1}{Re} + \bar{v}_t \right) a \bar{r} \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \bar{r}} \right] - \frac{A \rho_2^3}{10^{20} \cdot 4.1868^2} c_1^2 c_2 \bar{\rho}^3 \exp\left(-\frac{A_{r2}}{T}\right),$$

where dimension ω_2 translated into SI.

and equation for fuel concentration c_2 considering the rate of a chemical reaction.

Reverse transition from relatively excessive concentration $\bar{\bar{c}}$ to mass concentrations of components C_n at $n = 1, 3, 4$ carried out according to the formula

$$c_n = [(\bar{c}_n)_2 - (\bar{c}_n)_1] \bar{\bar{c}} + (\bar{c}_n)_1 \pm \frac{v_n m_n}{m_2 v_2} c_2,$$

and at $n = 5$ – according to the formula

$$c_5 = [(\bar{c}_5)_2 - (\bar{c}_5)_1] \bar{\bar{c}} + (\bar{c}_5)_1.$$

The process of combustion of gaseous fuel is carried out at relatively low speeds relative to the speed of sound. Therefore, the kinetic energy of the gas can be neglected. Then, a substitution similar to that introduced for the concentration can also be used for the total enthalpy, which leads to the normalization of the total enthalpy [17–18]

$$\bar{\bar{H}} = \frac{H - H_1}{H_2 - H_1} = \bar{\bar{c}}.$$

Here

$$H_1 = (c_p)_1 T_1 + (c_2)_1 h_2^*, \quad H_2 = (c_p)_2 T_2 + (c_2)_2 h_2^*.$$

In this case, the value of the temperature of the mixture is calculated by the formula

$$T = (H - c_2 h_2^*) / c_p = \left[H_1 + (H_2 - H_1) \bar{\bar{H}} - c_2 h_2^* \right] / \sum_{n=1}^N c_{pn} c_n$$

The value of the density of the gas mixture necessary for further calculations is found by the formula

$$\rho = \frac{p}{R_0 T \sum_{n=1}^N c_n / m_n}.$$

We passed to dimensionless variables and Mises variables. We passed to dimensionless variables using the characteristic quantities a, u_2, ρ_2 :

$$\bar{x} = \frac{x}{a}, \bar{r} = \frac{r}{a}, \bar{u} = \frac{u}{u_2},$$

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_2}, \text{Re} = \frac{u_2 a}{\nu}, \bar{G}_1 = \frac{G_1 a}{u_2}, \bar{G}_2 = \frac{G_2 a^2}{u_2}, \bar{N}_1 = \frac{N_1}{u_2}, \bar{N}_2 = \frac{N_2 a}{u_2}.$$

When passing to dimensionless variables, both sides of the equation are divided by $\frac{\rho_{oc} u_{oc}}{a}$.

Therefore, the source term takes the form:

$$\frac{a}{\rho_{oc} u_{oc}} \omega_2 = -\frac{a}{\rho_{oc} u_{oc}} \frac{A \rho_{oc}^3}{10^{20} \cdot 4.1868^2} c_1^2 c_2 \bar{\rho}^3 \exp\left(-\frac{A_{r2}}{T}\right) = -\frac{A}{10^{20} \cdot 4.1868^2} \frac{a \rho_{oc}^2}{u_{oc}} c_1^2 c_2 \bar{\rho}^3 \exp\left(-\frac{A_{r2}}{T}\right).$$

As a result, we get

$$\bar{\rho} \bar{u} \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho} \bar{v} \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \bar{r}} = \frac{1}{Sc \bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left[\bar{\rho} \left(\frac{1}{Re} + \bar{v}_t \right) \bar{r} \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \bar{r}} \right] - A_{r1} c_1^2 c_2 \bar{\rho}^3 \exp\left(-\frac{A_{r2}}{T}\right).$$

Here we introduced the notation:

$$A_{r1} = \frac{A}{10^{20} \cdot 4.1868^2} \frac{a \rho_{oc}^2}{u_{oc}}, \quad A_{r2} = \frac{3.00 \cdot 4.1868 \cdot 10^4}{8341.41} K.$$

The turbulence equation is written in full form

$$\begin{aligned} \rho u \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial x} + \rho g \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r} &= P_v - D_v + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\rho r (v + c_0 v_t) \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\rho r (-v + (c_1 - c_0) v_t) \right) \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r}; \\ \rho u \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial x} + \rho g \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial r} &= \bar{\rho} \rho_2 \bar{u} u_2 \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t a u_2}{\partial \bar{x} a} + \bar{\rho} \rho_2 \bar{g} u_2 \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t a u_2}{\partial \bar{r} a} = \rho_2 u_2^2 \left(\bar{\rho} \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho} \bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right); \\ \bar{P}_v &= \rho_2 u_2^2 \left(\bar{\rho} c_1 F_2 \left(\bar{v}_t \bar{G}_1 + A_1 \bar{v}_t^3 \bar{G}_2^3 \right) + \bar{\rho} c_2 F_2 A_2 \bar{N}_1 \left(\frac{1}{Re} + \bar{v}_t \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \bar{G}_1^{\frac{1}{2}} + \bar{\rho} c_3 \bar{v}_t \left(\frac{\partial^2 \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}^2} + \bar{N}_2 \right) \right); \\ \bar{D}_v &= \rho_2 u_2^2 \left(\frac{\bar{\rho} c_3 \bar{v}_t^2}{\bar{a}_{sz}^2} \bar{G}_1^2 + c_4 \bar{\rho} \bar{v}_t \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{r}} + \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial \bar{r}} \right| \right) + \frac{\left(\bar{\rho} c_6 \bar{v}_t (\bar{N}_1 \bar{d}_w + \bar{v}_{t,\omega}) + c_7 \bar{\rho} F_1 \frac{1}{Re} \bar{v}_t \right)}{\bar{d}^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_2 u_2^2 \left(\bar{\rho} \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho} \bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right) &= \rho_2 u_2^2 (P_v - D_v) + \frac{1}{\bar{r} a^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\rho_2 \bar{\rho} \bar{r} a \left(\frac{u_2 a}{Re} + c_0 u_2 a \bar{v}_t \right) \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t u_2 a}{\partial \bar{r} a} \right) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{\bar{r} a^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\bar{r} a \rho_2 \bar{\rho} \left(-\frac{u_2 a}{Re} + (c_1 - c_0) u_2 a \bar{v}_t \right) \right) \frac{u_2 a}{a} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}}. \end{aligned}$$

Otherwise, taking into account $\bar{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{a u_2}$, in each term a dimensionless factor is formed $\rho_2 u_2^2$:

$$\rho_2 u_2^2 \left(\bar{\rho} \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho} \bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right) = \rho_2 u_2^2 \left(\bar{P}_v - \bar{D}_v + \frac{1}{\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\bar{\rho} \bar{r} \left(\frac{1}{Re} + c_0 \bar{v}_t \right) \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right) + \frac{1}{\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\bar{r} \bar{\rho} \left(-\frac{1}{Re} + (c_1 - c_0) \bar{v}_t \right) \right) \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right).$$

Reducing by $\rho_2 u_2^2$, we get

$$\bar{\rho} \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho} \bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} = \bar{P}_v - \bar{D}_v + \frac{1}{\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\bar{\rho} \bar{r} \left(\frac{1}{Re} + c_0 \bar{v}_t \right) \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right) + \frac{1}{\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\bar{r} \bar{\rho} \left(-\frac{1}{Re} + (c_1 - c_0) \bar{v}_t \right) \right) \left(\frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right);$$

Thus, the differential equations take the form:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \bar{\rho}\bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho}\bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{r}} &= \frac{\partial}{\bar{r}\partial \bar{r}} \left[\bar{\rho} \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + \bar{v}_t \right) \bar{r} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{r}} \right], \\ \frac{\partial(\bar{\rho}\bar{u}\bar{r})}{\partial \bar{x}} + \frac{\partial(\bar{\rho}\bar{g}\bar{r})}{\partial \bar{r}} &= 0, \\ \bar{\rho}\bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho}\bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial \bar{r}} &= \frac{1}{\text{Pr}\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left[\bar{\rho} \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + \bar{v}_t \right) \bar{r} \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial \bar{r}} \right], \\ \bar{\rho}\bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{c}_2}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho}\bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{c}_2}{\partial \bar{r}} &= \frac{1}{\text{Sc}\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left[\bar{\rho} \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + \bar{v}_t \right) \bar{r} \frac{\partial \bar{c}_2}{\partial \bar{r}} \right] - A_{r_1} c_1^2 c_2 \bar{\rho}^3 \exp(-A_{r_2}/T), \\ \bar{\rho}\bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{\rho}\bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} &= \bar{P}_v - \bar{D}_v + \frac{1}{\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\bar{\rho}\bar{r} \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + c_0 \bar{v}_t \right) \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}} \right) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{\bar{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{r}} \left(\bar{r}\bar{\rho} \left(-\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + (c_1 - c_0) \bar{v}_t \right) \right) \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial \bar{r}}. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (3)$$

In closing relations, we pass to dimensionless variables as follows. We have

$$p = \rho \frac{R_0}{m} T = \rho_2 \frac{R_0}{(m)_2} T_2.$$

From here we find the expression for density: $\bar{\rho} = \frac{mT_2}{(m)_2 T}$.

We transform the conditions for the required ones.

At $\bar{x} = 0$ and $0 \leq \bar{r} < 1$ we have: $\bar{u} = 1, \bar{H} = 1, c_n = (c_n)_2$.

At $\bar{x} = 0, \bar{r} \geq 1$ and at $\bar{x} > 0, \bar{r} \rightarrow \bar{r}_\infty$: $\bar{u} = \frac{u_1}{u_2}, \bar{H} = 0, c_n = (c_n)_1$.

On the jet axis at $\bar{x} > 0$: $\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{r}} = 0, \bar{g} = 0, \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial \bar{r}} = 0, \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial \bar{r}} = 0$.

A feature of the problem under consideration is that the flow propagates along the axis x from left to right and there are no boundary conditions in the right part of the flow region, since they do not affect the propagation processes. Accordingly,

it is expedient to describe the process in von Mises coordinates and introduce the stream function ψ according to the relations [16-19]:

$$\rho u r = \psi \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r}, \quad \rho g r = -\psi \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}$$

(hereinafter, we omit the sign of non-dimensionality in equations and relations). The formally introduced second coordinate is $\xi = x$.

The derivatives in the equations are replaced according to the dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\rho g r}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi}, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial r} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} = \frac{\rho u r}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi}. \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the dimensionless equation of conservation of the total mass is uniquely satisfied.

The left sides of the equations are transformed into

$$\rho u \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial}{\partial r} = \rho u \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} - \frac{r}{\psi} \rho v \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \right) + \rho v \frac{r}{\psi} \rho u \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} = \rho u \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi}.$$

The components of the right sides of the equations are transformed as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\rho r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right] &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{r}{\psi} \rho u \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\rho \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + v_t \right) r \frac{r}{\psi} \rho u \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \right] = \\ &= \frac{1}{\psi} \rho u \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\rho^2 \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + v_t \right) r^2 \frac{u}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \right] = \frac{\rho u}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\frac{\rho^2 u r^2}{\psi} (v_t + v_t) \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

The value of the transverse coordinate process of discretization of equations and required for the calculation is found by the formula conditions. The differential equations for the conservation of substances take the form:

$$r^2 = 2 \int_0^{\psi} \frac{\psi d\psi}{\rho u}, \text{ what we will return to in the}$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} = \frac{1}{\psi} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \psi} \left[\frac{\rho^2 u r^2 (v_t + v_t)}{\psi} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \psi} \right], \\ \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial \xi} = \frac{1}{\text{Pr} \psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\frac{\rho^2 u r^2 (v_t + v_t)}{\psi} \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial \psi} \right], \\ \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \xi} = \frac{1}{\text{Sc} \psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\frac{\rho^2 u r^2 (v_t + v_t)}{\psi} \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \psi} \right] - A_{r1} \frac{c_1^2 c_2 \bar{\rho}^2}{u} \exp(-A_{r2} / T), \\ \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial \xi} = \frac{P_v}{\rho u} - \frac{D_v}{\rho u} + \frac{1}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\frac{\rho^2 u r^2}{\psi} \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + c_0 v_t \right) \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial \psi} \right] + \\ + \frac{1}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\frac{\rho r}{\psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + (c_1 - c_0) v_t \right) \right] \left(\frac{\rho u r}{\psi} \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial \psi} \right). \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$T = \frac{H_1 + (H_2 - H_1) \bar{H} - c_2 h_2^*}{c_p}, \quad \bar{\rho} = \frac{m T_2}{(m)_2 T}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_1 &= \left| \frac{\rho u r}{\psi} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \psi} \right|, \quad G_2 = \left| \frac{\rho^2 u^2 r^2}{\psi^2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \psi^2} \right|, \quad N_1 = \left| \frac{\rho u r}{\psi} \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial \psi} \right|, \quad N_2 = \left| \frac{\rho u r}{\psi} \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial \psi} \right|. \\ P_v &= \rho c_1 F_2 \left(v_t G_1 + A_1 v_t^4 G_2^{\frac{2}{3}} \right) + \rho c_2 F_2 A_2 N_1 \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + v_t \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} G_1^{\frac{1}{2}} + \rho c_3 v_t \left(\frac{\rho^2 u^2 r^2}{\psi^2} \frac{\partial^2 v_t}{\partial \psi^2} + N_2 \right). \\ D_v &= \frac{\rho c_5 v_t^2}{a_{sz}^2} G_1^2 + \frac{\rho u r c_4 \rho v_t}{\psi} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial \psi} + \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial \psi} \right| \right) + \frac{\left(\rho c_6 v_t (N_1 d_w + v_{t,\omega}) + c_7 \rho F_1 \frac{1}{\text{Re}} v_t \right)}{d^2}. \end{aligned}$$

At the entrance $\xi = 0$ the following conditions are imposed on the computational domain:

$$\text{At } 0 \leq \bar{\psi} < 1: \bar{u} = 1, \quad \bar{H} = 1, \quad c_2 = (c_2)_2, \quad \bar{v}_t = 0.007.$$

$$\text{At } 1 \leq \bar{\psi} < \bar{\psi}_\infty: \bar{u} = \bar{u}_1, \quad \bar{H} = 0, \quad c_2 = (c_2)_1, \quad \bar{v}_t = 0.005.$$

$$\text{At } \xi > 0 \text{ we have at } \psi = 0: \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{\psi}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial \bar{\psi}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial c_2}{\partial \bar{\psi}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial \bar{\psi}} = 0.$$

$$\text{At } \psi \rightarrow \psi_\infty: \bar{u} = \bar{u}_1, \quad \bar{H} = 0, \quad c_2 = (c_2)_1, \quad \bar{v}_t = 0.005.$$

Transition to discrete variables

We write the equations in a single form:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial \xi} = \frac{1}{\delta_U \psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left(K h_\psi \frac{\partial U}{\partial \psi} \right) + f_U.$$

$$\text{Here } K = \frac{\rho^2 u r^2 (v_l + v_t)}{\psi},$$

$$U = u : \delta_U = 1, f_U = 0;$$

$$U = \bar{H} : \delta_H = \Pr(= Sc), f_H = 0;$$

$$U = c_2 : \delta_{c_2} = Sc, f_{c_2} = A_{r1} \frac{c_1^2 c_2 \bar{\rho}^2}{\bar{u}} \exp(-A_{r2} / T).$$

On the right side of the equations, r^2 – the square of the dimensionless radial coordinate. We calculate it with the second order of accuracy

$$(r_{i,j}^s)^2 = (r_{i,j-1}^s)^2 + 2 \frac{\psi_j^2 - \psi_{j-1}^2}{\rho_{i,j-1}^{s-1} u_{i,j-1}^{s-1} + \rho_{i,j}^{s-1} u_{i,j}^{s-1}}.$$

This is the formula for i - section; s – of the previous section. To reduce the entries and iteration sequence number for i - th section. For the amount of calculations, we first calculate $i-1$ - th section. r^2 calculated according to the data

$$K_{i,j} = \frac{(\rho_{i,j})^2 u_{i,j} (\bar{r}_{i,j})^2}{j} (v_l + (v_t)_{i,j}),$$

$$\text{where } \bar{r}_{i,j} = (r_{i,j})^2 / h_\psi^2.$$

$$\text{At } j=0 \text{ accepted } K_{i,0} = 0 \text{ and } \bar{r}_{i,0}^2 = 0.$$

We approximate the equations for a fictitious node $(i+0.5, j)$ with the second order of accuracy in both coordinates:

$$\frac{U_{i,j}^{s+1} - U_{i-1,j}}{h_\xi} = \frac{1}{4\delta_U j h_\psi^2} \left[(K_{i,j+1}^s + K_{i,j}^s)(U_{i,j+1}^{s+1} - U_{i,j}^{s+1}) - (K_{i,j}^s + K_{i,j-1}^s)(U_{i,j}^{s+1} - U_{i,j-1}^{s+1}) + (K_{i-1,j+1} + K_{i-1,j})(U_{i-1,j+1} - U_{i-1,j}) + (K_{i-1,j} + K_{i-1,j-1})(U_{i-1,j} - U_{i-1,j-1}) \right] + \frac{(f_U)_{i,j}^s + (f_U)_{i-1,j}}{2}.$$

Multiply both sides of the equation by $4\delta_U j h_\psi^2$ and we give similar terms with the selection of terms with elements of the previous time section:

$$(K_{i,j+1}^s + K_{i,j}^s)U_{i,j+1}^{s+1} - (K_{i,j+1}^s + 2K_{i,j}^s + K_{i,j-1}^s + 4\delta_U j / \sigma)U_{i,j}^{s+1} + (K_{i,j}^s + K_{i,j-1}^s)U_{i,j-1}^{s+1} = -2\delta_U j h_\psi^2 (f_U)_{i,j}^s - (K_{i-1,j+1} + K_{i-1,j})U_{i-1,j+1} + (K_{i-1,j+1} + 2K_{i-1,j} + K_{i-1,j-1} - 4\delta_U j / \sigma)U_{i-1,j} - (K_{i-1,j} + K_{i-1,j-1})U_{i-1,j-1} - 2\delta_U j h_\psi^2 (f_U)_{i-1,j},$$

Where $\sigma = h_\xi / h_\psi^2$. Let us introduce the notation:

$$\begin{aligned} a_j^{(U)} &= K_{i,j+1}^s + K_{i,j}^s, \quad c_j^{(U)} = K_{i,j}^s + K_{i,j-1}^s, \\ b_j^{(U)} &= a_j^{(U)} + c_j^{(U)} + 4\delta_U j / \sigma, \quad d_j^{(U)} = -2\delta_U j h_\psi^2 (f_U)_{i,j}^s, \\ g_j^{(U)} &= -(K_{i-1,j+1} + K_{i-1,j})U_{i-1,j+1} - (K_{i-1,j} + K_{i-1,j-1})U_{i-1,j-1} + \\ &+ (K_{i-1,j+1} + 2K_{i-1,j} + K_{i-1,j-1} - 4\delta_U j / \sigma)U_{i-1,j} - 2\delta_U j h_\psi^2 (f_U)_{i-1,j}. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, the finite difference equation takes the form:

$$a_j^{(U)}U_{i,j+1}^{s+1} - b_j^{(U)}U_{i,j}^{s+1} + c_j^{(U)}U_{i,j-1}^{s+1} = d_j^{(U)} + g_j^{(U)}.$$

If we assume that the values of the coefficients are known $\alpha_{j-1}^{(U)}$ and $\beta_{j-1}^{(U)}$ in $U_{i,j-1}^s = \alpha_{j-1}^{(U)}U_{i,j}^s + \beta_{j-1}^{(U)}$, then to calculate the values of the sweep coefficients we obtain the formulas: Selection $g_j^{(U)}$ requires additional computer memory, but at the same time, in the process of successive approximation, it significantly reduces the amount (time) of calculations and makes it possible to use a larger step in ξ .

The implementation of boundary conditions is carried out in the usual mode.

$$\frac{\partial v_t}{\partial \xi} = \frac{P_v}{\rho u} - \frac{D_v}{\rho u} + \frac{1}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left[\frac{\rho^2 u r^2}{\psi} \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + c_0 v_t \right) \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial \psi} \right] + \frac{1}{\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi}$$

In the second group, the approximation of equations and the sweep process are similar to those used in the first group.

The calculation for a fixed section consisted of three stages. In the first stage, the components of the finite difference equations were calculated with the exponents of the previous section: $\tilde{r}_{i-1,j}$, $K_{i-1,j}$, $g_j^{(\dots)}$ and organized a zero approximation. The other two stages represented iterative processes in terms of speed and other indicators. The stage of the iterative process in terms of speed includes the calculations $\tilde{r}_{i,j}$, $K_{i,j}$, $g_j^{(u)}$, running process and checking the fulfillment of the approximation condition $\max_{i=0,1,\dots,Ny} |u_{i,j}^m - u_{i,j}^{m-1}| < \varepsilon_u$ iterative process by (m is the iteration number). If the condition is not met, then the iterative process in speed continues. If the condition is met, then the transition to the second stage is carried out, where the turbulence, fuel concentration and total enthalpy indicators for the next approximation are determined by the sweep method and the approximation in terms of total enthalpy and density is checked. If the condition for the total enthalpy and density is not met, then the calculations for the speed are resumed (the second stage) and the third stage is repeated.

Results

Calculations were carried out in accordance with the above. The mass composition of air was given as $(c_1)_1 = 0.232$, $(c_5)_1 = 0.768$. The main flow rate was 61 m/c, and co-current – 18.3 m/c. Air temperature – $T_1 = 300\text{K}$, and combustible mixture – $T_2 = 300\text{K}$. Step of numerical integration over x – was equal to 0.001, on ψ – 0.02. When passing to

the dimensionless coordinate r data were presented with a constant step of 0.02.

$$\alpha_j^{(U)} = \frac{a_j^{(U)}}{b_j^{(U)} - \alpha_{j-1}^{(U)}c_j^{(U)}}, \beta_j^{(U)} = \frac{c_j^{(U)}\beta_{j-1}^{(U)} - d_j^{(U)} + g_j^{(U)}}{b_j^{(U)} - \alpha_{j-1}^{(U)}c_j^{(U)}}.$$

On fig. 1 shows isotherms in the field of intense heat and mass transfer, which were obtained with $a = 0.05\text{M}$.

Fig.1. Isotherms in the field of intense heat and mass transfer at $a = 0.05\text{M}$

Near the nozzle, the highest temperature is reached at a certain distance from the axis. Nonmonotonic behavior of isotherms up to $x/a \approx 60$ shows that the line of the highest temperature in the cross section first moves away from the jet axis. Reaching 1690 K at $r/a \approx 5$, $x/a \approx 60$, it moves towards the flow axis and after $x/a \approx 84$ the maximum temperature in the section coincides with the axial temperature. Further, the axial temperature increases and at $x/a \approx 698$ reaches 2052 K. After that, the highest temperature in the cross section, i.e. axial temperature decreases. At the end of the conditional section $\bar{H}_{ocb} = 0.01$ on the jet axis the temperature is $\approx 761\text{K}$. (fig.1).

Fig.2. Comparison of the calculation of the axial excess temperature with the experiment [5]:

Calculations have shown that in the initial section the maximum temperature will not be on the flow axis. At $a = 0.001\text{M}$ the largest radial coordinate of the highest temperature (690 K) in the section $r/a \approx 2.6$ observed at $x/a \approx 14$. The combination of the highest and axial temperatures (at 867 K) occurs at $x/a \approx 30$. The highest

temperature in the calculation area is 1134 K, and the axial temperature at the end of the conditional flame (at $\bar{H}_{ocb} = 0.01$) equal to 756 K.

Fig. 3. Curves of the largest (dotted) and axial (solid) temperature values along the dimensionless length of the torch at various

radii of the fuel nozzle: 1, 2 – 0.05 m; 3, 4 – 0.01 m; 5, 6 – 0.001 m

Note that each calculation was repeated in the Ansys Fluent 6.3 program code and the results of two calculations were compared. Ansys Fluent is a powerful tool for streamlining the design and engineering process in the field of computational fluid and gas dynamics. In Fluent, it is possible to simulate the combustion process in furnaces, taking into account turbulence, heat and mass transfer, chemical reaction, and flow swirl. A typical field of mass concentrations of components was obtained using two programs. On fig. 4 they were compared with $x/a=5$.

Fig. 4. Graphs of mass concentrations of components at $x/a = 5$

If at $x/a=1$ the initial jet is expanded by about one and a half times, then at $x/a = 5$ (fig. 4) – up to three times. The highest concentrations of combustion products are formed first at the jet boundary, and then they move away from the flow axis. Molecular nitrogen, which makes up the bulk of the air, gradually penetrates towards the axis of the jet.

The concentration of combustible gas decreases in the graphs, both due to the expansion of the distribution area, and due to the reaction with oxygen.

Conclusions

Methods for introducing the Schwab-Zel'dovich functions and relatively excess enthalpy are shown for the case of turbulent combustion of methane in a co-current air flow with a finite velocity flowing out of the nozzle. A numerical method based on finite-difference

schemes is proposed for solving the problem of the propagation of an axisymmetric fuel jet in a co-current air flow in von Mises variables using the Sekundov $\nu_t - 92$ turbulence model.

For the numerical solution of the problem, an approximation scheme of the second order of accuracy in both coordinates was used, which gives a more accurate picture of the object and the physical essence of the combustion process. An algorithm and a calculation program with internal and external iterations for the longitudinal velocity and other indicators of heat and mass transfer processes have been developed. Based on the results of the computational experiment and comparison with field experiments, it was revealed that with an increase in the concentration of fuel in the composition of the main flow mixture, expansion and elongation of the flame front are observed.

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